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The new O'pen Skiff 3.5 sail: an Aerodynamic consideration

Gianmario Broccia*^a

^a *Second Level Specializing Master in Aerospace System Engineering;*

M.Sc. in Energy Engineering, graduated at the University of Cagliari – DIEE;

Racing SailCoach for the Royal Yachting Association and the Italian Sailing Federation (FIV)

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of the new 3.5 sail in the O'pen Skiff Class came along with the possibility of either choosing a new shorter top-mast or a classic one. The difference between the two is in the length, which causes the second one to have an excess coming out from the sail, resulting in the generation of higher aerodynamic drag.

This paper will attempt to provide some insights, at least from a mere aerodynamic point of view, whether the new mast is worth buying or not.

1. Introduction

In 2022 the O'pen Skiff International Association finally introduced the new 3.5 m² sail for the U12 category. The new sail, dacron-made and fully battened, is intended to better allow younger and entry-level sailors to express the maximum speed with a minor effort.

The 3.5 sail shows a smaller height than the old 3.8 and the use of the classic top-mast results in a long excess we will simply refer to as “Tip”. To overcome this issue, a new composite top mast was created ad-hoc to match the height of the 3.5 sail and,

nonetheless, both pieces are considered (for now) class-legal. The classic and the new mast only differ by the top part length and are commonly referred to in the market as O'pen Skiff Mast 390 and O'pen Skiff Mast 330 (1), a designation we will keep in short as M390 and M330.

The paper wants to provide a guide for the sailor who is considering buying a new mast and needs an objective indication of whether the M330 is worth the change or not. The goal is to determine how much the Tip of the upper M390 will affect the aerodynamic drag concerning the whole Sail-Tip coupling.

* Corresponding author. Tel.: (+39) 348-4665186

E-mail address: gianmario.broccia@gmail.com

Linkedin: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/gianmario-broccia-827737165/>

Figure 1 - The former 3.8 sail and the 3.5 new one. Image from NZSailing.com (2).

2. Measurements and assumptions

To set up a series of base calculations it was necessary to collect a few measurements from a boat kindly provided by the Yacht Club Quartu (3) O'pen Skiff Team.

Figure 2 - The 3.5 sail used for the analysis.

First of all, we measured the maximum and minimum diameters for the top piece of the M390 (henceforth respectively D_{topmax} and D_{topmin}) then we took a precise measurement of the mast lengths h_{top} and

h_{bottom} and the length of the Tip coming out from the 3.5 sail, h_{tip} , which was found to be 0.5 m in order to keep a correct sail shape (having the possibility to trim a set of straps). Finally, the length h_{sail} was measured as well considering the perpendicular distance between the top and bottom base of the sail.

Mast Measurements (m)			
B	1.95	D_{topmin}	0.025
b	0.63	D_{topmax}	0.04
h_{sail}	2.7	h_{tip}	0.5
h_{top}	2.0	h_{bottom}	1.9

Table 1 - M390 sections measurements.

The analysis will be as simple as possible, yet searching a certain grade of detail, and this will imply a series of assumptions:

- The shape of the Tip will be considered as a cylinder with a diameter equal to the averaged maximum and minimum diameters of the excess part only (D_{tip}), calculated with a proportion;
- When calculating the Drag Force for the Tip, one value of windspeed at 3.65 m height will be considered as representative;
- The sail itself is assimilated to an isosceles trapezoid of major base B, minor base b and height h;
- Any sail-tip interaction will not be accounted for as it would require a study with a 3D model, which computation would be too heavy.

3. Windshear and Drag Coefficient

3.1 Windshear

When considering the wind intensity at altitudes of a few meters, the friction exerted by the ground cannot be neglected. In this sense, the wind will be slowed down by roughnesses such as buildings or forests. On the other hand, a flat surface like the water will produce little effect on the wind intensity, which will be free to increase its intensity in a matter of meters (as in the case of a 3.9 m long mast).

Figure 3 - Wind Intensity profiles in function of the height and ground roughness.

The relation between the windspeed V and the height is generally expressed as:

$$\frac{V}{V_0} = \left(\frac{h}{h_0}\right)^\alpha \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where:

- V_0 is the wind intensity measured at a given height h_0 (m/s);
- α is the Windshear Coefficient.

Known α , the wind intensity can be calculated for any other height h . In this case, the maximum and minimum values of interest are 0.7 m and 3.4 m (hereafter h_{lower} and h_{upper} respectively) as the sail was found to be 0.7 m above sea level when the hull is in the water. Accounting for a windshear coefficient equal to 0.1 for the flat water (4), Eq.1 simply becomes:

$$\frac{V_{3.4m}}{V_{0.7m}} = \left(\frac{3.4}{0.7}\right)^{0.1} \approx 1.171 \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

which means the wind intensity on top of the sail will be 11.71% (11.79% for the Tip) higher with respect to the lower section and this highlights how the mast tip might be subject to the highest dynamic pressure.

Also, it is important to provide an idea of the type of flow the sail will be plunged in. The Reynolds number depends indeed on the fluid speed (air, in this case) and it can be calculated as:

$$Re = \frac{VL}{\nu} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

where:

- V is the speed of the object relative to the fluid, in this case, the windspeed (m/s);
- L is the characteristic linear dimension of the body (m);
- ν is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid (m^2/s)

Providing a windspeed range from 1 to 15 m/s and assuming a kinematic viscosity for the air equal to $1.4149 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ at 288 K (5), the Reynolds Number

ranges from 133,000 to 2,000,000 for the bottom part of the sail, from 51,000 to 760,000 for the top part of the sail and from 2,600 to 40,000 for the Tip, showing how the regime is mostly turbulent. This point cannot be underestimated as it strongly affects the Drag Coefficient (6), especially for the value we will need to consider for the Tip.

For the sake of convenience in the calculations, the range of 1-15 m/s for the windspeeds regards the height of 1 m and any other values of interest (such as for the 0.7 m, 3.4 m and 3.65 m heights) is calculated with Eq.1.

3.2 Drag Coefficient

Shed some light on this first point, the other side of the analysis is represented by the Drag Coefficient which can be considered as a dimensionless parameter that quantifies how much a body is aerodynamic. The higher the coefficient and the less aerodynamic the object will be, as the following relation shows:

$$C_d = \frac{2F_d}{\rho V^2 A} \quad (Eq.4)$$

where:

- F_d is the drag force (N);
- ρ is the density of the fluid (in this case the air) in kg/m^3 ;
- V is again the speed of the object relative to the fluid, in this case, the windspeed (in m/s);
- A is the reference Area in m^2 .

When deciding what area to choose, as reported by the Nasa Glenn Research Center (7), if we expect the drag as being caused by friction between the air and the body, the right idea would be to choose the real area of the airfoil. On the other hand, if we think of drag as being a resistance to the flow (as in the case of a cylinder or a body that does not generate lift, a more logical choice would be the frontal area of the body “seen” by the flow. Since the drag coefficient is usually determined experimentally by measuring the drag, it is our right to choose any area easy to measure. On the other hand, it must be noted that working in 2D the reference length for the C_d calculation can be simply the chord length (8) (9).

Such calculation is thus a long process that requests a certain degree of in-situ tests and, in this paper, such kind of condition is out of reach so that the C_d of the Tip will be considered qualitatively equal to 0.9 as Gumusel et. al. (10) report for a Reynold’s Number ranging roughly from 1,000 to 200,000, well within our range. To clarify, the cited paper refers to a 1:5 and an infinite aspect-ratio cylinder so we choose a middle value as the ratio in our case is 1:18.

As far as concerns the sail, the data available are not enough to establish a proper C_d without setting a wind tunnel and running real tests, which is again very unlikely under the given conditions.

The alternative is to search for existing literature in order to gather indicative data about what the C_d is likely to be for a generic sail and then proceed with different cases to assess the resulting drag force. In the lack of other options, the interest is to verify if these results are within the same order of magnitude, pointing to the same conclusion.

Figure 4 - Drag Coefficient vs Reynold Number (10).

Little et al. (11) and Otto Scherer (12) provide two insightful cases, although slightly different from this. In the first case, Little studies the induced drag produced by a yacht’s mainsail while sailing close-hauled, accounting for three different sails produced by North Sails, all with comparable drag coefficients so that a mean value of 0.0867 is adopted for this case. In the second case, Scherer analyzes the behavior in close-hauled and close-reaching of a double-slotted flapped wing sail designed by David Hubbard for the IYRU "C" class catamaran Patient Lady II. Along with this, a wing-mast model is also analyzed. In both cases, Scherer considers a low and high-camber model of which only the first is considered in this paper for both models. The experimental data plotted by Scherer were analyzed in this study with the Webplotdigitizer Software (13), which reliability was proven, for example, by Drevon et.al (14), to gather precise values for any point of interest.

It was decided to consider the highest value of the C_{dmax} and the one related to the maximum Lift Coefficient point $C_{dmaxlift}$. In the first case, the two

values are respectively 0.276 and 0.604 and, in the second case, 0.325 and 0.543. It must be noted that the maximum value of the lift coefficient is obtained for a close-hauled angle, while the maximum value of the drag coefficient manifests in close reach, according to Scherer’s measurements.

Figure 5 - The low-camber wings analyzed by Scherer. The mast-wing model is on the left and the double-slotted flapped wing is on the right.

Drag Coefficients		
Cylinder	0.9	
Little et.al	0.0867	
Scherer	Wing-Mast $C_{dmaxlift}$	0.276
	Wing-Mast C_{dmax}	0.604
	Flapped Wing $C_{dmaxlift}$	0.325
	Flapped Wing C_{dmax}	0.543

Table 2 - Summary of the drag coefficient to be considered.

4. Calculations

The Aerodynamic Drag Force on the Tip (in Newtons) $F_{tip(i)}$ for a given windspeed value “i” was calculated in a quite straightforward way:

$$F_{tip(i)} = \frac{C_d \rho V_{3.65m(i)}^2 A_{tip}}{2} \quad (Eq. 5)$$

where:

- C_d is equal to 0.9, as seen before;
- $V_{3.65m(i)}$ is the generic value of windspeed at 3.65 m height;
- A_{tip} is the frontal area of the Tip equal to the product between the mean diameter D_{tip} (found to be 0.027 m) and the Tip length;
- ρ is the air density taken equal to 1.225 kg/m³.

This simple way is chosen due to the simple shape of the Tip, which diameter does not change considerably over its length.

Concerning the sail, the matter is more complicated and must be faced considering the integration of the Drag Force at any given height over the whole length of the sail:

$$F_{sail(i)} = \int \frac{C_d \rho c_h V(i)^2}{2} dh \quad (Eq. 6)$$

where:

- c_h is the chord of the sail section at every given height h;

- h_{upper} and h_{lower} are the integration boundaries and equal to the heights at which the major base B and minor base b of the sail are placed with respect to the sea level.

It is now necessary to understand that the chord value and the windspeed vary for each given height value. While the windspeed V at the generic height h is represented by Eq.3, the chord value can be characterized by remembering the assumption of a trapezoid in place of the sail:

$$c_h = \frac{(b - B)h}{h_{sail}} + B \quad (Eq. 7)$$

Clearly, the chord will be equal to b at the top of the sail ($h = h_{upper}$) and equal to B at the bottom ($h = h_0 = h_{lower}$). Replacing Eq.3 and Eq.7, Eq.6 becomes:

$$F_{sail(i)} = \frac{C_d \rho V_{0(i)}^2}{2 h_0^{2\alpha}} \int \left[\frac{(b - B)h}{h_{sail}} + B \right] h^{2\alpha} dh \quad (Eq. 8)$$

The final result is then approximated by:

$$F_{sail(i)} = \frac{C_d \rho V_{0(i)}^2}{2 h_0^{2\alpha}} [1.625 h^{1.2} - 0.22222 h^{2.2}] \quad (Eq. 9)$$

At this point, only the integration boundaries h_{upper} and h_{lower} must be applied to complete the calculation.

The total Drag of the Sail-Tip system will be then obtained from:

$$F_{tot(i)} = F_{sail(i)} + F_{tip(i)} \quad (Eq. 10)$$

5. Results and Discussion

The final results are summarized in Fig.6. The Drag of the Tip was added as a control and the first result to point to is the curve given by the Drag Coefficient from Little. In this case, such a very low coefficient, associated with an America's Cup-like boat, depicts a very low total Drag Force so that the tip itself counts for a minimum of 0.3% to a maximum of 12.8%.

Taking into account the values gathered by Scherer, the situation changes deeply. The higher the drag coefficient, the higher the Drag Force so that the Mast Tip has a smaller role in the count. The green and yellow curves are associated with the maximum value of drag coefficient for the Flapped-Wing and the Mast-Wing models and the Tip counts up to 2.7% and

2.5%, respectively.

Finally, in the middle are the blue and grey curves related to the drag coefficient when the lift coefficient has its maximum value. In this case, the Mast Tip counts for up to 5% with the Wing-Mast and 4.4% with the Flapped-Wing.

Again, it is reminded that the maximum lift coefficient condition happens (according to Scherer) with an angle of attack typical of the close-hauled course, while the maximum value of the drag coefficient manifests in close-reach.

6. Conclusions

In this simple study the analysis of the aerodynamic effect owed to the M390 coupled with the new 3.5 sail was studied. The total Drag Force has been calculated in a sufficiently precise way over different values of windspeed and drag coefficient. Given the results, the mast appears to produce a higher Drag, as expected, without creating an excessive difference

Figure 6 - Final Results for every Cd and Windspeed value.

between the two masts.

However, even though the higher drag produced by the M390 is not particularly marked, it cannot be considered negligible and the M330 seems to be desirable, especially in the case of young athletes aiming to high-level races.

Moreover, according to the official dealer Tahe Sport, the M330 is more responsive, especially in strong winds, where a heavier sailor should be able to better maintain a correct heel and flow on the sail.

This work is however from a mere aerodynamic point of view and the author recommends the creation of another analysis of the M390 and M330 from a structural point of view, to assess the dynamic responses and make further assumptions about the right choice of the rig for a given sailor.

7. Acknowledgments

The presented paper was created by the author with full autonomy without the request or funding from other organizations or third parties. This work is to be intended as a free contribution to the O'pen Skiff class and a guide for athletes in the need of an objective point of view in deciding how to set up their racing rig.

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